

Preparing Higher Educational Administrators to Meet Global Standard: The Nigerian Factor

Dr. Godfrey Chukwumeka Nnadiye
Department of Educational Management, Faculty of Education,
Rivers State University, Nigeria

Abstract

This paper explores the issues of dwindling standard of higher education in Nigeria. Indeed, the issue of poor standard of higher education has become a subject of public discussion in virtually every enlightened gathering. This situation has been attributed to various factors but generally, the impression has revolved around inefficiency on the administrative performance of the higher educational administrators in our institutions. In the present realities, the world is becoming a global village with the adoption of current technology and skills to create, manage, process, manipulate and organize a vast varieties of activities in the schools to be both efficient and effective in achieving results. The paper therefore examined the present situation in the schools and the travails of the education system, the expectations from the higher educational administrators and the need for these higher educational administrators to be specially trained to meet the global challenges. The major challenges to the training of the higher educational administrators were highlighted while ways to overcome such challenges provided. A number of recommendations were proffered which included that Information and Communication Technology (ICT) should be made compulsory in the training of higher educational administrators to prepare them for modern administrative excellence among others.

Keywords: *Higher Educational Administrators, Global Challenges, Effectiveness, societal changes.*

Suggested citation: Nnadiye, G.C. (2024). Preparing Higher Educational Administrators to Meet Global Standard: The Nigerian Factor. *Scientia. Technology, Science and Society*, 1(1), 12-19. DOI: 10.59324/stss.2024.1(1).02

Introduction

All over the world, education has been regarded as a very important index of development. Indeed the key agent for National Development. The National Policy on Education (NPE, 2014) described education as a very important instrument for achieving National Development.

Okeke (2001) argued that what a nation makes of her educational system, to a large extent, dictates the tempo of the march to nationhood and self-sufficiency. He maintained that the educational system had been replete with plethora of experiments bordering on quality and quantity of human operations. In other words the higher educational administrators has continued to witness challenges as a result of the changing demands of the society, new ideas experience and expectations. Such challenges included, curriculum changes, increased students performance and infrastructural challenges. The report of the India School Leadership Institute (2013) observed that there is rising expectations and demands on schools requiring new breed of school administrators

with skills and knowledge to address the challenges. The issue being stressed therefore is quality management of the schools to achieve excellence even in the face of these challenges.

Unfortunately, there had been serious complaints about the quality and standard of education. It has become a subject of public discussion in virtually all enlightened gatherings. The general opinion is that the higher educational administrators are not living up to their duties. The higher educational administrators are the educational leaders on the school system. The nature and quality of leadership provided by them are of tremendous value to the Nigerian society.

Izuagba (2014) observed that the higher educational administrators as major force in ensuring the mobilization of people and materials towards achieving higher educational goals in the schools, they are to maintain conducive atmosphere for the attainment of national goals and objectivities by putting into consideration a number of factors in line with current challenges in the schools.

Two major ideas informed this work. One is the fact that the higher educational administrators occupy strategic position in the leadership of the schools and have been classified by the public as deficient in current skills to achieve results. Mulford (2003) opined that school leaders remain of crucial importance for the continued improvement of education. He further expressed worry that the existing approaches to higher educational leadership may create unintended consequences that fuel the current problems in the quality of higher educational administrators. Secondly, the travails of the higher education sector have been further compounded by the rapid technological changes in the world without corresponding preparations by the leadership of the school. Capacity building therefore becomes necessary for the higher educational administrators on whose shoulders the affairs of the school revolve.

Presently, we are in the information and communication technology era. It remains the stock in trade of any establishment including education. Communication to staff, students, the government, the host community and indeed decision-making in the schools require the ICT for efficiency, speed and accuracy. In support of the foregoing, Olalekan (2009) stated that school leaders require enhanced skills and capacities in various aspects of strategic leadership of people, school facilities, budgeting, staffing and accountability. He cited a number of studies conducted on how higher educational administrators have been performing their roles. For instance, the study conducted by Akpa (1999) showed that higher educational administrators ranked the responsibilities they performed in order of priority with a discovery that teaching and instructional supervision were treated with less vigor.

The higher educational administrators are expected to acquire remarkable skills and abilities, attributes, knowledge and tasks to make the education system more utilitarian and result oriented than what it had been. Combs, Harris and Edmonson (2015) identified that higher educational administrators should be current in the following skills:

1. To communicate information and ideas in appropriate communication skills of listening, speaking, reading and writing using modern technological provisions.
2. To exhibit attributes of adjusting actions using logic and reasoning to identify strengths and weaknesses of alternative solutions to problems.
3. To be conscious of cost-benefit approach in order to maximize benefit.
4. To have knowledge of the principles and methods of curriculum design, teaching as well as evaluation of outcomes.
5. To make use of strategic planning and effective co-ordination of human and material resources.

6. To be trained in the study of human behaviour, individual differences in ability, personality, interests and ways to motivate staff and students to achieve results.

The situation in the schools has been the appointment of higher educational administrators from a pool of senior scholars with or without specialized training in educational administration. Nnabuo (2011) observed that it is dehumanizing to see unskilled, unqualified and incompetent scholars pose around the school claiming to be leaders but are virtually empty. The situation cannot hold water due to recent innovations and trends in the education sector. Some of these innovations are manifest in the use of modern instructional materials both audio and audio visuals, using the computer and other aspects of information technology, evaluation of learning outcomes, modern school equipment, storage, processing, programming and retrieval of data, etc. These areas of innovation call for specialized training and retraining of higher educational administrators.

Uwazuruike (1991) opined that innovation as the introduction of new ideas, techniques, materials and or technologies to improve educational processes and outcome. It is therefore necessary for new ideas to be injected into the administration of the schools to correct some of the inadequacies of the past. Caldwell (2011) posited that higher educational administrators should possess the skills and philosophies that would show how deeply or broadly educational innovations, reforms or changes should be practiced.

The inadequacies in the higher educational system have led to public outcry on the state of the public higher institutions and the ability of the higher educational administrators resulting in teacher apathy and poor performance of the students.

Nduka (2007) states that whatever deviates from that, which is expected, we commonly say it is abnormal or unexpected. People have continued to wonder why the quality of the school products remain in the lowest ebb despite government efforts to provide enormous resources to the institutions. The situation continues to raise concerns as to the preparedness of the higher educational administrators. According to the Wikipedia of Free Encyclopedia (2015), programme for higher educational administrators should cover the following courses:

- Introduction to higher educational administration
- Introduction to higher educational planning, supervision and inspection.
- Economics of education
- Management of change and innovations in higher education
- Educational administration of higher education in Nigeria
- Principles and theories in higher educational management
- Practicum in higher educational management
- Research in higher educational management
- Information and communication technology
- Educational law
- Classroom management and organization
- Education finance
- Educational management policies and planning
- Research method etc.

Therefore, this paper is intended to portray the need for capacity building for higher educational administrators towards acquiring current skills and training for improved productivity and moral standards in the institutions of learning.

Why should Higher Educational Administrators be specially Trained to Meet Global Standard

The appointment of higher educational administrators by the visitor cannot continue to hold sway. Bottoms and O'niel (2001) stated that gone are the days when higher educational administrators were expected to do a little more than 'hold' the institutions. This practice may have worked in the past say 1960s – 1980s when the institutions were few and students enrolment was manageable. The prevailing situation shows a picture of inadequacies in our higher institutions including unpredictable teacher/students ratio due to poor statistical projections, poor academic performance which can be attributed to many factors, lack of character training on the part of the staff and students etc. The above situation could also be attributed to the outcome of non professional activities of the school leaders, thereby producing students without appropriate ethical standards and worth, necessary to move the nation forwards. Indeed the fallen standard of education has been blamed on the adoption of unprofessional as higher educational administrators.

The world is gradually becoming a global village using the information and communication technology as its medium of communication. The products of the schools in Nigeria could operate in other parts of the world. They are expected to fit in properly as their counterparts. The implication is that the higher educational administrators who are the school leaders need to be trained and retrained in line with current trends in education and in the society in general because a leader cannot open what he does not have.

Apart from the above, virtually all the higher institution programmes require technological touch in terms of receiving information, storing, retrieval programming and even evaluation of learning outcomes. These activities will make the duties of the higher educational administrator easier and more result oriented.

The changing needs and aspirations of the students as well as the society in general require appropriate leadership and coordination of school programmes to create the enabling climate for cooperation. Higher educational administrators need to update their knowledge and skill to cope with the changing aspirations and needs. There should be periodic evaluation of school programmes and students activities; there should be coordination of other areas such as the counseling of students, health services, available school resources and the implementation of the curriculum accordingly. Marshall (2011) observed that higher educational administrators are responsible for ensuring equitable schedules that maximize teaching and learning devoid of sugar-coat/criticisms to keep peace and avoid hurting feelings. These are areas the higher educational administrators should regularly have grip and be properly abreast of the trends of events.

The school and its immediate environment especially the host community and the government should relate effectively to be relevant to each other. Ihebereme (2006) described the school and the community as two outstanding but inseparable and indispensable features of any society be it tradition or contemporal. There is need for the higher educational administrators to acquire the technique of social relationship to the school and the host community for the symbiotic relationship of the duo.

Moreover, there is need to equip the higher education administrators with current principles and theories to prepare them in the lines of authority, definition of duties, selection and placement of

staff and other administrative duties requiring the knowledge of administrative theories and practice.

Challenges to the Training of Higher Educational Administrators

Dearth of instructional facilities in the higher institutions of learning constitute a major problem. Capanham (2014) observed that instructional facilities are critical in supporting academic goals hence the need to assess the condition, adequacy and appropriateness of school facilities. Instructional materials such as electronic gadgets to expose the higher educational administrators to the rudiments of statistical studies, projectors and other materials to learn record keeping, storage, programming and retrieval of information. These materials help the learners to be abreast of their roles about projections for student enrolment and attrition, teacher-pupil ratio etc for effective administration of the schools. Moreso, there is high cost of books especially published materials and other electronic devices. Izuagba(2006) noted that government should provide modern infrastructural facilities and teaching materials in their required quality and quantity to meet the already set standards in education. Thus there is need for the government, nongovernmental organizations and philanthropists to assist higher institutions in their areas of need.

The presence of short cut university admissions in Nigeria today paves way for the production of unqualified educational leaders. The issue of differences in culture, tribe, unequal development and educationally disadvantaged states have untold effects on the quality of education system. The concept of federal character has led to undue preferences in admissions of unqualified candidates in the higher institutions resulting in the output of unintelligent graduates as educational leaders to man the institutions. As at present, there are some basic study programmes and shortcut study centres as affiliate of universities in the country that hurriedly produce graduates to flood the educational system.

Rapid Societal Changes

The society is dynamic in all spheres including the education sector. Education is a unit of the society; it exists to serve the society and therefore should be relevant to the society. While the higher educational administrator is being trained for a particular societal need and aspiration such societal needs and aspiration could be phased out necessitating a need to retain and update knowledge even at a short while. It is in line with the foregoing that Bar-tal and Rosen (2009) stated that to achieve school objectives, there should be a drastic change including setting new educational objectives, preparing new curriculum, re-writing school textbooks and retraining school administrators.

The general conception of higher educational administrators as the most senior of the entire teacher with or without specialization in higher educational administration still affects the need for their training. The policy makers tend to posit that the most senior teachers have gathered enough experience to run the schools. Apart from years of experience, there is need for training in the theory and practice in line with prevailing experiences to withstand the challenges as they come.

Overcoming the Challenges of Higher Educational Administrators

The higher educational administrators requires in-service training in form of seminars, conferences and workshops to update his knowledge, skills and abilities in line with the changing societal needs

and aspirations. Such trainings should be tailored to current issues and technological challenges aimed at improving the quality of the schools.

Provision of learning materials in higher institutions is very important. The government, educational agencies, NGOs and philanthropists should be encouraged to provide these facilities in their quality and quantity to equip the higher educational administrator with the knowledge, skill and abilities to serve. This is necessary especially the information and communication technology facility to train for data processing. This is a step in the right direction in meeting the increasing pace of globalization and technological change (Iheonunekwu, Kanu and Ndom, 2012).

Also foreign and locally published textbooks should be made accessible to the learners to broaden their knowledge. The issue of shortcut university admission and basic studies where students are hurriedly produced as graduates should be avoided.

The issue of disadvantaged states, religious sentiments as well as the federal character should not be used to the detriment of quality education. If these sentiments are continued to pervade the education system, the quality of the schools will continue to deteriorate with a corresponding effect on national development.

The notion of adopting higher educational administrators without specialization in educational administration is to say the least irrational. There is need for specialization in the theory and practice of higher educational administrators in addition to experience especially at this time of technology and reason.

Conclusion

This paper has attempted to X-ray the present situation relating to the performance of higher educational administrators in the Nigeria institutions.

Efforts were made, expressing the public outcry on the poor performance of the higher educational administrators as a result of their inadequacies in background and professional training. The travails of the education system in the country have been further accessed by the rapid technological changes in the world without a corresponding preparation of the educational leaders. Efforts were made to outline the reasons why higher educational administrators should be specially trained as well as possible course content in the universities.

Major challenges facing the preparation of higher educational administrators were looked into. Such challenges include: the dearth of modern technological facilities and teaching materials in the higher institutions such as quality published textbooks (foreign and local), ICT gadgets to expose the learners to modern technological devices to be applied at completion of their studies in the school etc.

The presence of shortcut admission requirement and basic studies by some institutions based on federal character or disadvantaged states remains a challenge. Such sentiments reduce quality of the products by producing misfits as higher educational administrators to the detriment of the schools. There is the challenge of the rapid societal needs and aspiration which continue to necessitate the training and retraining of educational leaders.

Moreso, the general conception by the policy makers of higher educational administrators as the most senior staff irrespective of professional training has continued to perpetuate inefficiency in administration of higher institutions.

However, this paper has made efforts to proffer possible solutions to the above challenges so that higher educational administrators will live above board in their roles as key agents for national development.

Recommendations

Having established in this paper that there is need for specialized training for higher educational administrators, it has therefore become obvious that the hue and cry about poor performance of the higher institutions cannot be unconnected with the background of the higher educational administrators compounded by other inadequacies in the higher institutions.

Therefore, this paper recommends as follows:

1. There should be regular training and retraining of higher educational administrators through short course programs, seminars, conferences and workshops to re-orientate them on the current challenges facing the higher institutions.
2. Various levels of government and relevant agencies, non-governmental agencies (NGOs) should be encouraged to support the higher institutions especially in the provision of libraries, technological gadgets and devices.
3. As the world becomes a global village in terms of rapid technological advancement, efforts should be made to make ICT compulsory in the training of higher educational administrators to prepare them for modern techniques of communication, recording, reporting, and
4. Storage of information among others.

References

- Bar-Tal, D., & Rosen, Y. (2009). Peace education in societies involved in intractable conflicts: Direct and indirect models. *Review of Educational Research*. <https://doi.org/10.3102/0034654309333057>
- Bottoms, G., & O'Neil, K. (2001). Retrieved from www.sreb.org
- Caldwell, B. (2011). Systems leadership for innovation in education. *Innovation Unit*. Retrieved from www.innovationunit.org
- Capanham. (2014). Different types of instructional materials presentations. *Slideshare*. Retrieved from <https://www.slideshare.net/different>
- Combs, P. J., Harris, S., & Edmonson, S. (2015). *Educational leadership: Communication skills for leaders*. Retrieved from www.ascd.org/publican/educational-leadership
- Federal Republic of Nigeria. (2014). *National policy on education*. Abuja: Federal Ministry of Education.
- Ihebereme, C. (2006). The school and the community relationship. In Ike-Obioha, Ihebereme, & Ikwuegbu (Eds.), *The school and community* (pp. 112–134). Owerri: Divine Mercy Publishers.
- Iheonunekwu, S., Kanu, J., & Ndom-Uche. (2012). An examination of the role of higher education and entrepreneurship education in Nigeria's national transformation. *Journal of the Nigerian Association for Educational Administration and Planning (NAEAP)*, 8(3), 56–78. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11092-012-9176-x>

- India School Leadership Institute (ISLI) Report. (2013). *India School Leadership*. Retrieved from www.indiaschoolleaders.org
- Izuagba, N. J. (2006). *Universal basic education: Public research commitment*. Owerri: Alphabet Nig. Publishers.
- Izuagba, N. J. (2014). *The school environment: In teachers, schools, and society*. Owerri: Pearl Publishers.
- Marshall, K. (2011). Principals' evaluation rubrics. *Marshall Principal Rubric*. Retrieved from www.principalrubric.com
- Mulford, B. (2003). School leaders: Challenges, roles, and impact on teachers and school effectiveness. *Educational Leadership*, 45(2), 34–49. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-1-137-50073-3_2
- Nduka, E. C. (2007). *Statistics has it that...* Inaugural Lecture Series No. 57, University of Port Harcourt.
- Nnabuo, P. O. M. (2011). *Supervision and inspection: A human paradigm*. Inaugural Lecture Series No. 74, University of Port Harcourt.
- Okeke, B. S. (2001). *Quality management and national goal attainment in education: The case of Nigeria*. Inaugural Lecture Series No. 28, University of Port Harcourt.
- Olalekam, A. (2009). Professional training of secondary school principals in Nigeria: A neglected area in the educational system. *Institute of Education, Olabisi Onabanjo University*. Retrieved from www.ufe.edu/FEAP_summer2002
- Uwazuruike, C. N. (1991). *Educational planning and national development: A Nigerian perspective*. Awka: Mekslink Pub. Nig.
- Wikipedia. (2015). *School of education*. Retrieved from <https://en.wikipedia.org/school-of-education>

